

D6.10 Communication and dissemination plan - Final Report

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Executive summary

The present public document presents an update of the VitiGEOSS project dissemination and communication plan outlined at M7, aiming at reaching as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the activities and results derived from the project. BSC and EUT are responsible for designing and implementing VitiGEOSS communication and dissemination strategy, but all consortium partners will be involved in it.

The channels and platforms considered in the communication and dissemination plan are: social media channels, official website, materials to be distributed in key events, media relations to specialized media outlets, scientific publications, the organization of workshops and training activities, and attendance to strategic conferences, fairs and congresses where the project can be presented and the organisation of stakeholder engagement events, among others.

This deliverable updates the dissemination plan and reports on communication activities from M1 to M18.

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List of abbreviations

<i>D</i>	<i>Deliverable</i>
<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EO</i>	<i>Earth Observation</i>
<i>KPI</i>	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>
<i>PR</i>	<i>Public relations</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction and scope of this deliverable

The VitiGEOSS Communication and Dissemination Plan aims to outline the communication and dissemination activities planned throughout the project. These activities aim to **raise awareness** on the project and its **results** among the target audiences and as many relevant actors as possible, **support exploitation** and ensure market uptake of the developed platform, and **share the know-how generated** from the project with the scientific and industrial community.

This document defines the tools and activities that have been carried out throughout the first year and a half of the project, as well as the upcoming activities to be carried out during the second period to ensure exposure and dissemination of the project itself and its results to the scientific and industrial community, in particular stakeholders in the wine sector.

Regarding the communication and dissemination actions done, this document presents the outcomes of VitiGEOSS activities, and the impact achieved, including the creation of the project website and a set of promotional materials, the participation in events to raise awareness on the intelligent services the project is building, the production of the first press release and the organisation of the first local stakeholders' event, to mention the main activities.

On the other hand, a plan for upcoming activities and calendar is included, detailing the scope and goals of the next events to be organised, as well as plans for training activities, events in which we envisage to participate and scientific publications.

The evaluation of the key performance indicators (KPIs) for each communication and dissemination activity at M18 is included to assess the progress made during the first project period.

1. Communication and dissemination plan

EUT and BSC lead VitiGEOSS communication and dissemination activities within the project, but all consortium partners are actively involved in these activities. Dissemination and communication actions are considered by the consortium as an instrument to speed up results' exploitation during and after the project as it helps to raise awareness amongst key stakeholders.

The main goals of the VitiGEOSS project communication and dissemination strategy are:

- To **increase the visibility** of VitiGEOSS and its outcomes in Europe and beyond
- To develop communication and dissemination activities to **facilitate knowledge transfer** to stakeholders
- To promote the use of **Earth Observation services and Climate services** in the agriculture sector
- To **build capacity** among current and potential developers and users of commercial products within the wine sector and beyond
- To **showcase new capabilities** combining smart services and make them **available for uptake** by the European wine industry and global markets

VitiGEOSS communication and dissemination strategy aims at respecting partners' IPR and exploitation interests, with due care to not raise unrealistic expectations in end-users of the project solution, which may have a detrimental effect on the market demand.

The main language of the communication and dissemination activities organised by VitiGEOSS is English. However, specific materials are translated into Spanish, Italian and Portuguese for a broader reach, with support from EUT (Spanish), LINKS and UNINA (Italian), and SYM (Portuguese).

In the following sections, a description of target audiences, key messages and channels used and to be used are defined.

1.1 Target audience

Five stakeholder groups were identified at the beginning of the project execution as target audiences of the communication and dissemination activities, including: academia, industry, end-users/customers, policy makers, and society at large. Detailed information on identified stakeholder groups is presented in Figure 1.

A list of key contacts and target stakeholders, in continuous update, is stored in the VitiGEOSS internal collaborative platform (ensuring that no personal information is included or distributed). This list has been regularly updated with new contacts, including individuals who sign-up to the project mailing list through a form circulated on the project communication channels.

Scientific and academic community

- Universities, institutes and research centers on researching Earth Observation (remote sensing, geoanalysis), climate forecasting, phenology, vine fertilisation and disease monitoring, sensing, applied artificial intelligence, etc.
- Research and technology organizations
- Attendees to trade exhibitions covering the project's fields (EU Conference on precision agriculture, EuroGEOSS workshop, ONEOVITI Interlational, International Organisation of Vine and Wine, etc.)
- Sister projects (VISCA, e-shape, ENVISION, SAFERS, NextLand, SUSTUNTECH, FIRE, etc.)

Industry, end users / customers

- Farmers, wine producers, R&D technicians working in the wine sector, EU wine industry, downstream operators (wine producers and distributors), upstream operators (fertilised producers)
- Viticulture sector and ICT companies and companies in the agriculture value chain (machinery, applications, etc.).
- Wine cooperatives, agricultural organisations, clusters (e.g. INNOVI, Plataforma tecnológica del vino, Confederação dos Agricultores de Portugal (CAP), CONFAGRICOLTURA, CCBUL, Irish farmer's association, FEV - the Spanish Wine Federation, etc.)
- Climate services and Earth Observations industrial community (companies providing services) (e.g. EARSC - European Association of Remote Sensing Companies)
- Industrial trade fairs and exhibitions (VINITALY, VINEXPO, ALIMENTARIA, Fair of Agricultural Machinery, wine fairs, etc.)

Policy makers

- Governmental bodies in charge of agricultural resources management (e.g. Departments / Ministries of Agriculture) and environment, Governmental Wine Institutions / Institutes (INCAVI, VITINNOV), European bodies managing earth observations (Copernicus, European Space Agency, etc.)
- Networks, associations, platforms (COPA-COGECA, Comité Européen des entreprises vins, EuroGEO, COPTA, etc.)
- Environmental organisations
- Other initiatives (EU wine market observatory)
- Standardisation bodies and technical committees.

Society at large

- Rural communities
- Mass media
- Wine consumers, consumers associations (WWCA - World Wine Consumer Association, International Wine Clubs Association, OCU - Spanish Consumers Association, etc.).
- Wine sector top influencers (GLOBAL: Madeline Puckette, Maximilian Riedel, Kelly Mitchell, Carolyn Evens Hammond, Jamie Goode, Liz Palmer, Meg Maker - Terrior Review, Joey Casco - TheWineStalker, Andrea Ziggrossi, Gaetano Saccoccio - Natura Delle Cose FRANCE: Emmanuel Delmas, Louise Binns, Nicolas de Rouyn, Fabiel Lainé, Marina Giuberti, Julien Miquel, Tanisha Townsend, UK: Tim Atkin, Jancis Robinson, Fiona Beckett SPAIN: José Pañín, Josep Roca, Amaya Cervera - Spanish Wine Lover, Luis Gutiérrez Santo Domingo ITALY: Andrea Ziggrossi, Francesco Saverio Russo)
- EU citizens

Figure 1: Stakeholders' map defining main target audiences' groups and subgroups

1.2 Channels

The dissemination and communication activities of the VitiGEOSS project use a wide range of channels and actions, ranging from publication of project results and news on the project website and social media channels, preparation of promotional materials, scientific publications, organisation of workshops and specific stakeholder engagement events, to the representation of the project in key events (see Figure 2).

Besides the aforementioned project channels, all partners have used and will make use of their own channels (websites, presence on social media and corporate newsletters / publications) to disseminate news about VitiGEOSS and reach a broader audience.

Figure 2: VitiGEOSS Dissemination and Communication Channels

1.3 Key messages

Key messages defined in **D6.9 - Communication and dissemination plan - First Report** continue to be valid as base messages to deliver to each of the stakeholder groups identified. If necessary, the messages will be tailored as the project advances, along with VitiGEOSS activities and results.

General VitiGEOSS messages include:

1. *The VitiGEOSS project uses European Open Earth Observation Services (EOS) and Climate Services for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental and local level.*
2. *The VitiGEOSS project develops innovative vineyard management solutions by integrating and improving existing tools that couple relevant information, such as satellite imagery and in-field sensors.*
3. *VitiGEOSS will be the first application offering a single-entry point to integrated services for weather and climate predictions, crop management, disease management, business operations and sustainability assessment.*
4. *The VitiGEOSS project will respond to current and future viticulture challenges by providing forecasts, data and recommendations to wine producers to optimise vineyard management.*
5. *VitiGEOSS is an EU H2020 project that will boost vineyard sustainability while supporting adaptation to climate change.*

Academia

- The VitiGEOSS project will advance the state-of-the-art techniques for weather and climate forecasts, monitoring of crop phenological stages as well as irrigation and fertilization needs, prediction of phenology stages and yield, and disease early prediction, risk assessment and recommendations on treatments.
- The VitiGEOSS platform will be fed with free-of-charge satellite imagery, other Earth Observation and climate prediction products from the European Copernicus Programme and NASA, coupled with in-field and near in-field data to extract useful indicators for a better management of vineyards and optimisation of agricultural practices.
- Machine Learning and new mathematical models will be used to detect and predict the vineyards' phenological states based on weather and climate observations and forecasts, in-field cameras and satellite imagery to support a better planning of operations.
- Key crop indicators will be used for the zonal delineation of vineyards to help define precision agriculture management strategies.
- Artificial Intelligence techniques will be used for the analysis and integration of multiple data sources to develop novel disease management and resource optimisation services.
- The scientific results of VitiGEOSS will be openly available to support further research activities.

Industry, consumers and end users

- The project will offer a commercial web platform to the viticulture sector, integrating information from intelligent services, to support farmers and producers to optimise vineyard management processes by making the most of open European data and resources.
- The project will validate the potential benefits of data fusion techniques for monitoring vineyards which could derive in a downscaling of the decision-making area granularity offered by Copernicus based solutions. This would produce better management strategies and costs optimization, by also supporting sustainable practices.
- VitiGEOSS will provide sub-seasonal and seasonal climate predictions, recommendations for crop and disease management, and tools for the management of business operations and sustainability of the vineyard.
- The VitiGEOSS platform will help farmers tackle the most critical vineyard diseases scheduling the preventive treatments according to diseases' evolution, using less chemicals and adapting their production methods to minimise damages to the environment.
- The VitiGEOSS information services will help schedule optimal harvesting days and thus contribute to optimize the harvesting process and consequent winemaking, minimising the waste of resources and increasing the competitiveness of the wine sector.
- The VitiGEOSS services will be validated in three vineyards located in Italy, Spain and Portugal before their release.

Policy makers

- VitiGEOSS will help the agriculture sector adapt to climate change and thus minimise the use of recovery plans for weather-affected crops.
- The proposed solution promotes the potential of the Copernicus programme and European satellite data for agriculture.
- The VitiGEOSS information services will advance the development of services based on the use of Earth Observation Services.

- The VitiGEOSS platform will provide valuable information to public administrations to inform the design of environmental and agriculture policies as well as subsidies/funds in the event of emergencies, such as extreme weather events with critical effects for the harvest.

Society at large

- The implementation of the VitiGEOSS solution will contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions through the optimisation of operations that involve the use of fossil fuels.
- The solution will help reduce the amount of chemicals used in the fields, resulting in more sustainable practices for the environment and healthier wines for the EU consumers.
- The innovative solutions promoted by the project help mitigate the effects of climate change, reducing negative environmental externalities and promoting local economic growth.

2. Communication and dissemination management

2.1 Distribution of responsibilities

The VitiGEOSS dissemination and communication strategy includes three tasks with three subtasks each, foreseeing the active involvement and commitment of all project partners for presenting the project and its outcomes.

BSC is the **Communication and Dissemination lead beneficiary**, responsible for **coordinating WP6 activities**, ensuring the proper information exchange within the consortium and supporting the full dissemination of the project and its results. In addition, BSC will lead the organisation of three technical webinars (Subtask 6.2.1), the work on sharing the lessons learned in the project with the Climate Services community (Subtask 6.3.1), and the production of an executive summary at the end of the project highlighting the main results (Subtask 6.3.3).

EUT, through its Research Communication Office (RCO), will **support BSC in coordinating the WP** and will be the **partner directly responsible** for the development of the project's visual identity and website (Subtask 6.1.1). EUT will also be responsible to produce the **Communication and Dissemination Plan** (Subtask 6.1.2), the **production of communication and PR materials** and a demo video (Subtasks 6.1.3 and 6.2.3), and the coordination overview of the local stakeholder sessions at the General Assemblies. The RTO will also participate on the organisation of technical webinars.

End-users **MBD**, **MTSA** and **SYM** will organise a local stakeholder session at their facilities to engage local farmers and rural communities (Subtask 6.3.2).

In addition, **ELEAF** will lead the organisation of the participatory workshops (Subtask 6.2.2) and will be responsible for sharing the lessons learned in the project with the Earth Observations community. **BSC** and **UNINA** will play an active role by developing the contents for and participating in the trainings and seminars organised during the workshops.

2.2 Requirements

All communication and dissemination materials produced in the project (posters, presentations, promotional material, publications, etc.) and distributed in physical or electronic format (e.g.,

social media) have taken into account to display the EU emblem and funding text provided below, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869565.

In addition, results disseminated are recommended to include the following disclaimer:

[This result NAME] reflects only the author's view and the Agency / Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Scientific papers based on the research conducted in the project will be published in open-access repositories, mentioning in the acknowledgements the VitiGEOSS project name, as well as that funding was received by the European Union (EU)/Horizon 2020 (including grant number).

2.3 Monitoring and reporting

2.3.1 Activities reporting

Several excel files were prepared by the BSC to register all communication and dissemination activities done by partners during the project execution, as well as monitor KPIs activities such as social media and website analytics, media impacts or scientific publications published.

All files are in the SharePoint online repository that is available to all partners. For more information on the different files created please refer to D6.9.

Table 1: Table to record the communication and dissemination activities performed by partners

Type of action	Primary audience reached with the action	Secondary audience reached	Title of the action	Location	Date	Number of people reached	of	Link	VitiGEOSS attendees/organisers (if applicable)

2.3.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs were assigned to several communication and dissemination activities planned in the project in order to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project (M42). These are listed in Table 2. See below the status of the KPIs set at M17, during the month of production of this deliverable.

Already at M17, some KPIs such as those for the Twitter activity have been achieved, denoting the efforts during the Covid-19 pandemic to disseminate the project using the channels available.

Table 2: Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M17	M42
Website	Number of website visits	Website Analytics	1,439	>3,500
	Number of pages viewed		3,756	>10,000
	Number of users		735	>1,500
	Average session time		03:17	>1 min
Social Media	Twitter: Number of followers	Twitter Analytics	172	>200
	Twitter: Number of tweets		322	>300
	Twitter: Twitter impressions		77,925	>50,000
	Twitter: Likes on tweets		453	>100
	Twitter: Retweets		380	>30
	Twitter: Mentions		65	>20
	YouTube: Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	3	>5
	YouTube: Number of video views		69	>300
Press Releases	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	1	>4
	Articles published in EU outlets		31	>25
Events	Number of events participated (congresses, conferences, etc.)	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	11	>20
	Number of local stakeholder sessions organised		1	3
	Number of technical webinars organised		0	3
	Number of participatory workshops organised		0	2
Publications	Number of scientific publications	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	0	5
	Number of articles in specialised magazines / outlets		5	3
Visual Materials	Number of posters produced	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	0	4
	Number of info-sheets produced		0	6
	Audio-visual materials		3	>2
	Project public reports		0	5
	Number of executive summaries		0	1
	Number of roll-ups		1	1
	Number of brochures		1	1

2.4 Risks and mitigation measures

The risks faced in the completion of activities planned in WP6 and potential mitigation measures were defined at M7. The risks, presented at Table 3, have been reviewed periodically to spot any new risks and determine if there is a need to put in place any mitigation actions.

Up until M17, only risk num. 3, regarding the effects of Covid-19 to dissemination, materialised. In that regard, the first local stakeholder event planned to be physically held was organised as an online event. On the other hand, the minimisation of the number of dissemination opportunities during the first period of the project was compensated by an increase of our activity in online channels, such as social media.

Table 3: Risks and mitigation measures

Risks	Risk level	Mitigation measures
#1 - Not enough users reached to provide a sustainable operation of the VITIGEOSS portal and services	Medium	Dedicated communication and dissemination strategies will be developed to ensure that a sufficient user-base can be reached. Involvement of relevant initiatives in the project Advisory Board that can help reach additional users.
#2 - Low stakeholder engagement in webinars, workshops and local sessions	Medium	Intensive communication campaigns promoting the activities through relevant channels will be run minimum 2 months in advance. Take advantage of project partners involved in relevant EU projects and initiatives to serve as ambassadors of VitiGEOSS and multiply project dissemination and stakeholder engagement.
#3 - Not enough dissemination opportunities due to COVID-19 effects	High	Thorough identification of activities and organisation of own events. Stronger emphasis on the organisation of online project activities (such as webinars) and possibility to accommodate initially planned physical activities remotely. Higher reliance on online channels (e.g. social media).
#4 - Not enough engagement on VitiGEOSS communication channels	Medium	Creation of more content for the project website and social media that engages stakeholders, increase the frequency of publication on project channels
#5 - Low project visibility	Low	Develop an appealing website and communication materials. Organise joint activities with other initiatives and projects (e.g., e-Shape, NextGEOSS)

3. Communication and dissemination tools and activities

3.1 Project Visual Identity materials

EUT has been in charge of defining the project’s image to be implemented across all the communication and dissemination channels, including the design of the logo, colour palette, and deliverable and presentation templates. EUT will ensure the correct use of the visual identity in all project-related materials. For more information regarding the VitiGEOSS visual identity, please refer to **D6.1 - Visual Identity and Project Website**.

3.2 Website

The project website (www.vitigeoss.eu) was launched in November 2020, as defined in **D6.1 Visual Identity and Project Website**. It has served since its creation as the main information platform for users interested in knowing more about VitiGEOSS. The website displays the project’s basic information, objectives, scenarios and expected outputs. Furthermore, the website is the central repository for all public material, including public results and deliverables, and gives access to the project’s Twitter and YouTube channel.

The website has been regularly updated by EUT with dissemination activities, media appearances and new deliverables, among other materials. Up to M17, a page for featuring information on related projects has been created, as well as pages to allocate information on dissemination activities, project news, project materials and a list of highlighted media impacts. Specific pages have been also created for project events, such as the first stakeholders’ session.

Figure 3: View of the project’s home page

A total of **3** project news articles on project activities and **11** articles on events have been published on the project website, curated by Eurecat.

For the second period of the project, new pages will be created following project activities and milestones, including the creation of specific pages for the allocation of information on each of the intelligent services, articles on dissemination activities and results.

Latest Past Events

- DEC
9
2021
- 09+01:00 December 09+01:00 2021
- VitiGEOSS project presented at the EIP-AGRI workshop "Farm data for better farm performance"**
- The VitiGEOSS project has been presented during the "Fira de Novembre de Vilanova i la Geltrú" online exhibition celebrated from 12th – 14th of November 2021.
- NOV
12
2021
- 12 12+01:00 November 12+01:00 2021 - 14 14+01:00 November 14+01:00 2021
- Eurecat disseminates VitiGEOSS during the "Fira de Novembre" online exhibition 2021**
- The VitiGEOSS project has been presented during the "Fira de Novembre de Vilanova i la Geltrú" online exhibition celebrated from 12th – 14th of November 2021.
- OCT
15
2021
- 15 15+01:00 October 15+01:00 2021
- Eurecat presents VitiGEOSS services to AURORAL project partners**
- Josep Pijuan, project partner and researcher at the Applied Artificial Intelligence Unit of Eurecat, presented VitiGEOSS project during the AURORAL project's Catalan working group meeting.

Figure 4: View of the events' page

3.2.1 Website analytics M1-M17

The VitiGEOSS website has Matomo installed on the platform's back end to monitor all the traffic and obtain monthly reports about the site's performance.

Table 4: Website analytics M1-M18

Website indicator	M1-M17
Visits	1,439
Page Visits	3,756
Users	735
Actions per visit	3,1
Average visit duration (min)	03:17

The website follows the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) directive, which came into force on October 31st, 2020. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics can only be tracked for users accepting analytic cookies. Estimating that only about 30% of the users accept the cookies before starting to browse the website, and considering that this 30% accounts for the data retrieved, we can estimate that we have received around 2,055 additional visits that couldn't be tracked. The same calculations can be extrapolated to the number of pages viewed, denoting that the project website has had more impact than what the statistics recorded through Matomo analytics show.

As for geographical and device traffic distribution, the majority of visits have come from Spain and followed by Italy, Germany, Sweden and the United Kingdom (denoting partners' efforts disseminating and communicating the project in their countries).

Figure 5: Visitors' country of origin by number of visits (left) and visitors map (right)

Pages	
PAGE URL	#IEWS
/index	,313
local-stakeholder-event-spanish	526
about-vitigeoss-project	302
vitigeoss-platform	240
portfolio-items	224
partners	182
event	127
pilots-vineyards	127
news-events	131
events	122
news	90
contact	74
help-us-identify-the-needs-of-...	92

On the other hand, top viewed pages include the homepage, the page of the local stakeholder event and informative pages on the project and the platform being developed.

Figure 6: List of top viewed pages

3.3 Promotional materials

EUT and BSC have been in charge of creating a set of visual materials to support the project’s dissemination activities and events, such as conferences, congresses, workshops or project events (local stakeholder sessions, webinars, etc.).

Three types of materials are going to be produced during the project execution: promotional material to print or use digitally, a final executive summary and audio-visual materials.

All materials available are stored digitally in the project’s internal repository and on the project website for broader dissemination. Promotional materials will be regularly updated according to project developments. Materials oriented to support the engagement with end-users will be translated into Spanish, Italian and Portuguese, responding to the VitiGEOSS project needs.

3.3.1 Digital & print promotional materials

EUT has designed and produced different types of promotional materials by month 5 of the project, including a **factsheet**, a **rollup**, a **trifold**, a **poster layout** and a **general presentation** to support the partners’ dissemination activities.

All materials produced follow the project’s visual identity guidelines (mentioned in section 3.1) and are available to all consortium members in a digital format. The materials are also available publicly on the project’s website in the page “**Newsletters & Promotional Materials**”.

Five different language versions were produced for the trifold. This material is **available in English, Catalan, Spanish, Italian and Portuguese**, aiming to be used in local stakeholder events and regional activities.

This set of materials will be updated at different stages of the project to include up-to-date information of the advances and results (M20, M32, M40).

Figure 7: View of VitiGEOSS flyer (left) and factsheet (right)

Other materials are planned to be produced during the project, including a **poster summarising the VitiGEOSS concept and platform** (planned for M20), which will be translated into the end-user’s native languages - Spanish, Portuguese and Italian - and **6 info sheets on the VitiGEOSS information services** to facilitate the transfer of the knowledge generated in the project into a wider audience (prepared in M32, and updated in M40).

3.3.2 Executive summary

Based on the project publications and public deliverables, an executive summary will be produced by M42 (as part of Subtask 6.3.3) to compile VitiGEOSS relevant results, impact and conclusions. The document aims to make the project conclusions easier to understand by policy makers and non-specialised audiences. Graphic materials gathered during the discussions in consortium meetings and stakeholder-oriented events (especially if there are opportunities for physical gatherings) will be used for the elaboration of the document.

The executive summary will be produced by the BSC with support from all partners and will be disseminated broadly on the VitiGEOSS website and other project channels (such as Twitter), as well as shared directly with any relevant contacts.

3.3.3 Audio-visual materials

Engaging audio-visual materials (e.g., videos) will be produced to present the key aspects of the project, including the project's deployment of information services and platform and its validation into demonstration sites.

Audio-visual material produced within the project framework will be published on the VitiGEOSS website and promoted on all project social media channels (Twitter & YouTube). A number of videos are planned, including the following:

- **Animated video of the project (M21):** this video, substituting the partners' short interviews in the D6.9 planning will consist of a 1 min - 1.30 min video in motion graphics to present the project in a nutshell, using illustrations and other resources.
- **Intelligent services / platform demo videos (M24 - M40)** - A series of videos that guide users through the different smart services developed in WP2 and the portal deployed by WP3 will be produced. These videos will also provide the necessary context to understand the project challenges, motivations and outcomes.
- **Final video (M41 - M42)** - A video compiling the results of the project, its applications and its benefits for the EU wine sector will be produced by EUT. It will include images on the work done in each of the pilot sites and short interviews with users, pilot site representatives and VitiGEOSS partners' short quotations on their contribution to the project.

The production of other audio-visual materials will be evaluated among the consortium if any other opportunities arise. Partners will be able to propose other video topics and produce complementary videos on their contribution to the VitiGEOSS project.

All videos will be produced in English, with subtitles available in Spanish, Italian and Portuguese to facilitate comprehension in the three pilot countries.

3.4 Social Media Strategy

EUT is responsible for managing the VitiGEOSS social media accounts and its content. A **Twitter channel for VitiGEOSS** has already been created (@Vitigeoss_EU - https://twitter.com/vitigeoss_EU) and is used to promote project materials and news. A YouTube channel was created as soon as the first project video was available (M12).

Other social media accounts, such as LinkedIn and Facebook, have been considered, and partners decided to **open a LinkedIn account (M18)** for the second period of the project, when more events are planned, and the project will deliver the majority of its results. For the moment, the use of Facebook has been dismissed, as after a consultation with project partners,

it was clear that the main stakeholders that may be interested in knowing more about project developments - professionals from the industry and academic community - do not use Facebook to get informed on sector news, research, and developments but rather to connect with family and friends.

The typology of content published in VitiGEOSS social media accounts has included:

- **Disseminating project activities:** sharing information on stakeholder engagement events, workshops, technical webinars and other dissemination activities organised by the project, including text and photos if possible.
- **Disseminating audio-visual and promotional materials** produced (to make the project more accessible/understandable).
- **Promoting** the project community of interest.
- **Sharing news and articles published on the website** to increase traffic.
- **Content curation:** sharing news on Earth Observation Services, Copernicus, phenology and climate forecasting models, sustainable agriculture case studies, technologies for the agricultural and viticulture sectors, disease management, business operation management, irrigation, and yield prediction, etc.

On the other hand, VitiGEOSS is using partners' corporate and personal Social Media accounts to contribute spreading the word, including accounts on Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, or Instagram.

The project coordinator has been in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

3.4.1 Twitter

Figure 8: View of VitiGEOSS Twitter account

The VitiGEOSS Twitter account is managed by EUT, with the support of project partners for its correct management. The main objective of this account is to raise awareness on the potential application of Earth Observation Services to enhance the sustainability of the wine industry, as well as to promote the project's intelligent services and platform to key stakeholders and the wine sector value chain. Twitter has also been used to connect with EU institutions and related projects and initiatives.

Relevant stakeholders and partners with a professional Twitter account have been followed by the VitiGEOSS account in order to boost the visibility of the account.

EUT has populated the account with content with inputs of consortium partners. For promoting specific events/campaigns, the tweets published included some graphical material created specially to make them more appealing. A Hootsuite, a tool facilitating the publication of content and activity monitoring, has been created for scheduling tweets and shortening URLs. Comments and answers have been managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

In section 3.4.1.2 of the D6.9, a content strategy was developed, mixing marketing content, branding and influence actions to maximise the project's impact, and encourage market uptake to secure a critical mass of early adopters of the smart services and platform among the

viticulture sector. At M17, the strategy continues to be valid and serves as guideline for all project partners posting about the project on Social Media.

A profile in Twitter

Figure 9: Some examples of content published on VitiGE OSS Twitter account

Analytics was activated at the beginning of the project in order to measure the Twitter KPIs (see Section 2.3.2 for more information) and other data about the account activity.

Figure 10: View of Twitter Analytics

As a result of all the activity, at M17 VitiGEOSS Twitter has 159 followers and has generated 386 tweets and more than 105K impressions and 94 mentions.

Table 5: Twitter analytics at M17

Twitter indicator	M1-M17
Followers	172
Tweets posted	322
Impressions	77,925
Mentions	65
Likes on Tweets	453
Retweets	380

3.4.2 LinkedIn

On the other hand, LinkedIn is a platform for the interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. VitiGEOSS account on LinkedIn, created at M17, allows project partners to connect with the industrial and academic community, as well as connect and engage with wine makers, Earth Observation, and viticulture 4.0 stakeholders.

Content creation in this account follows the social media guidelines specified in D.6.9, although the publication pace in LinkedIn is less frequent than Twitter. Content is based on project news, events organised and participated, and reports and publications produced in the framework of the project or by trusted sources.

The LinkedIn account is managed by EUT. All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed through this channel and can spread the word through their own corporate and personal channels by sharing the content published.

Publishing, as well as comments, answers and private messages are managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

Data on publications' impact will be retrieved from LinkedIn Analytics. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

Figure 11: View of VitiGEOSS LinkedIn account

3.4.3 YouTube

The European Commission recommends the use of audio-visual resources to bring the results of the research projects closer to the general public.

Following this recommendation, a YouTube Channel was created at M12 to allocate all videos produced during the project. At M17, the account counts with 3 videos available for the different sessions of the local stakeholders' event celebrated during November.

Figure 12: View of VitiGEOSS YouTube account

From the

creation of the account, VitiGEOSS YouTube channel has received 72 views, 136 impressions and 5,1 watch time hours, many of them during the days following the local stakeholders' event.

Your channel has gotten 72 views so far

Figure 13: View of YouTube analytics

3.4.4 Partners' channels

Each partner has transmitted VitiGEOSS news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.vitigeoss-project.eu or in the project Twitter account.

VitiGEOSS' partners impact in social media channels will reach more than **53K users on Twitter**, more than **112K on LinkedIn**, more than **1M Facebook followers** and **59K in Instagram**.

The corporate accounts used by partners are:

Table 6: Partners' social media accounts

PARTNER	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	Instagram
EUT	https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/	@Eurecat_News	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecat.org/	NA
LINKS	https://www.linkedin.com/company/linksfoundation/	@LinksFoundation	https://www.facebook.com/linksfoundation/	NA
SYM	NA	@SymingtonFamily	NA	@symingtonfamilystates
ELEAF	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eleaf/	@eleaf	NA	NA
BSC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/barcelona-supercomputing-center/	@BSC_CNS	https://www.facebook.com/BSCCNS	@BSC_CNS

PwC	https://www.linkedin.com/company/pwc-portugal	NA	https://www.facebook.com/pwcpportugal	@pwc_portugal
UNINA	NA	NA	NA	NA
MBD	NA	NA	https://www.facebook.com/MastroberardinoVinyards	@mastroberardinowinery
MTSA	https://www.linkedin.com/company/familiatorres	@FamiliaTorres @Torreswines	https://www.facebook.com/familiatorresoficial	@FamiliaTorres1870 @Familiatorreswines

Figure 14: Examples of messages published on partners social media accounts

3.5 Media relations

Press releases will be written and sent to relevant media at regular intervals throughout the project, focusing on the release of research results, milestones, meetings, attendance to or organisation of events etc., and connected with newsworthy initiatives when possible (e.g. EU Green Week, Rural Conventions, etc.).

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English for providing feedback (where appropriate), giving them the opportunity to adapt the documents in their corporate language and to circulate it among their regional media contacts.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented to a specific stakeholder group may be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator and Communication Leader (EUT). Also, VitiGEOSS partners will consider interview-offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to showcase the main project results to the media.

In the framework of the project, a **database with the contact details of partners' communication officers has been created**, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press releases and increase the project impact across Europe.

A **database with specialised media covering Earth Observation Services and innovations / technologies for the wine sector has been created**, primarily with outlets located in the partners' countries.

An initial list of **European / Global specialised media outlets** identified as relevant to promote VitiGEOSS outputs include:

Table 7: Initial list of specialised outlets

LIST OF SPECIALISED OUTLETS	Language
Mon-Viti - https://www.mon-viti.com	French
Future Farming - https://www.futurefarming.com	English
Geospatial world - https://www.geospatialworld.net	English
E&T Engineering and Technology - https://eandt.theiet.org/tags/earth-observation	English
InfoWine - https://www.infowine.com/en/news/news_cat_23.htm#	English
Vitisphere - https://www.vitisphere.com/world-wine-0-0-0-news.htm	English
WineSpectator - https://www.winespectator.com/news	English
HortNews - https://hortnews.com/articles/horticulture-news/viticulture-news/	English
DownToEarth - https://www.downtoearth.org.in	English
Tech.eu - https://tech.eu/about-us/	English
Farmers' weekly - https://www.fwi.co.uk	English
Farmers Guardian - https://www.fginsight.com	English
InfoAgro.com - https://www.infoagro.com/noticias/?ids=8	Spanish
La Semana Vitivinícola - http://www.sevi.net/es/3578/94/	Spanish
Vinetur - https://www.vinetur.com	Spanish
FuturENVIRO - https://futureenviro.es	Spanish
Agroinformación - https://agroinformacion.com	Spanish
Agroportal - https://www.agroportal.pt/autor/agroinformacion/	Spanish
El Correo del Vino - https://elcorreodelvino.com	Spanish
Enoviticultura - https://enoviticultura.quatrebcn.es	Spanish

At M10, the first press release of the project was produced, titled as “*European Consortium to Integrate Satellite and IoT Data to Develop Innovative Solutions for Smart Vineyard Management*”. The article summarised the main objectives and expected impacts of the project.

Apart from the consortium press release, EUT, BSC and TORRES adapted the press release to their audience, producing three country / regional version press releases.

- < Home
- News
- BSC News
- Events
- BSC in the Media
- Newsletter

European Consortium to Integrate Satellite and IoT Data to Develop Innovative Solutions for Smart Vineyard Management

30 September 2021

BSC participates in the European project VitiGE OSS, which aims to deploy innovative vineyard tools to support the sustainable management of the vineyard, offering integrated services for weather and climate predictions, crop and disease management, business operations and sustainability assessment.

The project is coordinated by the technological center Eurecat and makes use of artificial intelligence techniques for the analysis, optimisation and integration of multiple data sources that allow the development of services, with the aim to improve the local management of agricultural business operations at the economic and environmental level.

The Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) participates, together with the technological center Eurecat in the European consortium VitiGE OSS, which is developing an innovative vineyard management platform that provides forecasts, estimations and recommendations for wine makers to help boost vineyards' sustainability and adaptation to climate change.

Based on open-access satellite imagery and derived products and climate data from the European Copernicus Programme, together with other sources of data like drone and fixed camera images or in-field and machinery data, VitiGE OSS is developing intelligent services delivering weather and climate predictions, recommendations for crop and disease management, and tools for the management of business operations and sustainability of the vineyard.

BSC will oversee the co-design of the intelligent service for the delivery of weather and climate predictions together with the wineries Torres, Symington and Mastroberardino. This intelligent service will be integrated in the project innovative platform and will provide forecasts for the next days, weeks and months, useful for the management of the vineyard. BSC will also be responsible for the dissemination of the project results and will participate in the organization of webinars and participatory workshops targeting the wine and data collection sectors as well as potential service providers with the aim of spreading the use of earth observation and climate services.

Figure 16: VitiGE OSS press release published at BSC website

Figure 15: Publication of the project first press release in the VitiGE OSS website:
<https://vitigeoss.eu/european-consortium-satellite-iot-data-develop-innovative-solutions-smart-vineyard-management/>

Eurecat Àmbits de Coneixement Sectors Serveis Projectes Actualitat Contacte [in](#) [d](#) [f](#) [ca](#) [q](#)

Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per generar indicadors que ajudin a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes

Pàgina inicial / Notes de premsa, Smart Management Systems / [Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per generar indicadors que ajudin a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes](#)

Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per generar indicadors que ajudin a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes

El centre tecnològic Eurecat coordina el projecte europeu VitiGEOSS, que integra l'anàlisi de dades satel·litals, drons, maquinària i dades de sensors instal·lats en el camp, per desenvolupar nous serveis destinats a la millora de la gestió d'explotacions vitivinícoles.

Amb la finalitat de facilitar la gestió sostenible de vinyes, es generaran nous serveis intel·ligents de previsió climàtica, de detecció i previsió de la fenologia, de predicció del risc de malalties i de recomanació de tractaments, de generació d'indicadors del cultiu i predicció de producció o d'optimització en la gestió dels recursos, així com de seguiment d'indicadors de sostenibilitat.

En concret, la Unitat d'Intel·ligència Artificial Aplicada d'Eurecat s'encarregarà de l'aplicació de tècniques d'intel·ligència artificial per a l'anàlisi i la integració de múltiples fonts de dades que permetin desenvolupar nous serveis de gestió de malalties fúngiques, l'optimització de recursos i el seguiment d'indicadors de sostenibilitat, a fi d'obtenir millores en la productivitat de les explotacions vitivinícoles.

Finançat pel programa Horizon 2020 de la Unió Europea, el projecte VitiGEOSS integra i millora les solucions existents per acoblar les imatges de satèl·lit amb els sensors ubicats al camp, amb l'objectiu d'augmentar la resolució i fiabilitat de la informació provinent dels diferents satèl·lits aplicada al sector vitivinícola.

Segueix-nos a les xarxes socials!

[t](#) [d](#) [in](#)

Recent

-

La intel·ligència artificial obre les portes a millorar el diagnòstic de les malalties, a personalitzar els tractaments i a impulsar la medicina preventiva

febrer 11th, 2022
-

El Panel de tast de l'avel·lana incrementarà el nombre de tastadors especialitzats i les varietats per valoritzar aquesta fruita seca

febrer 7th, 2022
-

Eurecat patenta dues tecnologies per predir la conformabilitat i avaluar de forma més ràpida i econòmica la resistència a la fractura i a la fatiga de xapa metàl·lica

febrer 4th, 2022

Buscar

Figure 17: EUT version of VitiGEOSS press release (in Catalan)

A clipping study covering the project period shows that currently up to **33 articles in Spanish and English print and online media outlets** have been published, accounting for a total audience of **42M**. VitiGEOSS media impacts include key sectorial magazines in the wine sector such as [InfoWine.com](#), [El Correo del Vino](#), [Vinetur](#), [Tecnovino](#) or [Mundo Vino](#). The project was also published in generalistic newspapers across Spain with a large number of readers.

Table 8: Media articles featuring VitiGEOSS

Date	Media	Title	Typology	Audience	Link
23/01/22	Segre -Vint-i-dos	LLEIDA, POL D'INNOVACIÓ TECNOLÒGICA	Print	48000	Link
15/11/21	InfoWine.Com	VitiGEOSS European project for smart vineyard management	Online	1000	Link
09/11/21	Vinetur	Un consorcio europeo empleará inteligencia artificial usando datos geoespaciales para gestionar el viñedo	Online	20755	Link
21/10/21	El Correo del Vino	Familia Torres participa en el proyecto europeo VitiGEOSS para	Online	NA	Link

		desarrollar una plataforma de gestión inteligente del viñedo			
18/10/21	Tecnovino	Familia Torres se une al proyecto europeo VitiGEOSS para desarrollar una plataforma de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	1000	Link
14/10/21	MSN Spain	El cambio climático también calienta el vino	Online	36822488	Link
14/10/21	La Vanguardia	El cambio climático también calienta el vino	Online	1481323	Link
14/10/21	La Mañana	CREIXEN UN 6,3% ELS ALUMNES MATRICULATS EN ESCOLES AGRÀRIES	Print	5764	Link
09/10/21	De Vinos.es	Familia Torres participa en el proyecto europeo VitiGEOSS para desarrollar una plataforma de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	1000	Link
08/10/21	Agronews Comunitat Valenciana	Aplican modelos de inteligencia artificial usando datos geoespaciales para generar indicadores que ayuden a una gestión sostenible de las viñas	Online	1000	Link
07/10/21	30virtual	Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per generar indicadors que ajudin a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes	Online	1000	Link
06/10/21	Agronews Castilla Y León	Aplican modelos de inteligencia artificial usando datos geoespaciales para generar indicadores que ayuden a una gestión sostenible de las viñas	Online	1000	Link
05/10/21	Associació Catalana d'Enòlegs	Família Torres participa en el projecte europeu VitiGEOSS per desenvolupar una plataforma de gestió intel·ligent de la vinya.	Online	1000	Link
05/10/21	Fulls d'enginyeria	Eurecat utilitzarà IA per la gestió sostenible de les vinyes	Online	1000	Link
04/10/21	El Correo Del Vino	Familia Torres participa en el proyecto europeo VitiGEOSS para desarrollar una plataforma de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	1000	Link
02/10/21	RevistaAgricultura.com	VitiGEOSS integra la analítica de datos satelitales, drones y sensores para una gestión sostenible de las viñas	Online	1000	Link
02/10/21	Vinetur	Familia Torres participa en el proyecto europeo VitiGEOSS para desarrollar una plataforma de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	12532	Link
01/10/21	NoticiasDe.es	Familia Torres participa en el desarrollo de un proyecto de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	3915	Link

01/10/21	Gente Digital	Familia Torres participa en el desarrollo de un proyecto de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	11746	Link
01/10/21	Europa Press	Familia Torres participa en el desarrollo de un proyecto de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	576143	Link
01/10/21	Mundo Vino	Familia Torres participa en el proyecto europeo VitiGEOSS para desarrollar una plataforma de gestión inteligente del viñedo	Online	1000	Link
01/10/21	alimen21	Eurecat aplicará modelos de inteligencia artificial usando datos geoespaciales para generar indicadores que ayuden a una gestión sostenible de las viñas	Online	1000	Link
30/09/21	INNOVAGRI.es	Inteligencia artificial para conseguir una gestión sostenible de las viñas	Online	3915	Link
29/09/21	El Món.cat	Intel·ligència artificial per gestionar la vinya de manera més sostenible	Online	3915	Link
29/09/21	La Vanguardia	Eurecat Lleida aplicará IA en la gestión de sostenible de viñedos	Online	1481323	Link
29/09/21	L'Econòmic	Eurecat aplica models d'IA per a una gestió sostenible de la vinya	Online	1000	Link
29/09/21	El Punt Avui	Eurecat aplica models d'IA per a una gestió sostenible de la vinya	Online	250608	Link
29/09/21	Corporació Catalana de Mitjans Audiovisuals	Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes	Online	116144	Link
29/09/21	La Vanguardia	Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes	Online	1481323	Link
29/09/21	La República	Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes	Online	27410	Link
29/09/21	El Punt Avui	Eurecat aplica models d'IA per a una gestió sostenible de la vinya	Online	250608	Link
29/09/21	espai.media	Eurecat aplicarà models d'intel·ligència artificial usant dades geo-espacials per a una gestió sostenible de les vinyes	Online	1000	Link
29/09/21	Metadata	Eurecat aplicarà la intel·ligència artificial per millorar el conreu de les vinyes	Online	1000	Link

The planned calendar for **upcoming press releases** is as follows:

Table 9: Press release plan

VitiGEOSS press release plan		Partners responsible
M20	Release of intelligent services	EUT, BSC, LINKS, ELEAF
M30	Start of services validation in pilot sites (SYM, MTSA, MBD). Adaptation into three country-focused press releases.	EUT, SYM, MTSA, MBD
M40	Platform release	EUT, ELEAF
M42	Final project results.	EUT, BSC, SYM, MTSA, MBD

3.6 Participation to academic and industrial events

A wide range of conferences and academic fora are suitable for the exhibition and publication of the VitiGEOSS' results, covering, but not limited to, the topics of precision agriculture, earth observation services, climate & weather forecasting, smart agriculture, etc.

Dissemination in events mainly focuses on the partners' countries (Italy, Spain, and Portugal). Partners also have considered attending events taking place in other European countries targeting communities strongly related to the project objectives, certainly including the agriculture and wine community, but also the EO community, as well as other stakeholders for which the methodological approach and results of the project could be of interest (climate services community, Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) communities, etc.).

From M1-M18, project's partners have participated into **11 industrial and scientific specialised congresses and other relevant events** to present the project publicly. All these actions were used to make VitiGEOSS visible to the industry, scientific community and broader public. These actions helped raising awareness about the project goals amongst both the specialised audiences and the general public.

3.6.1 Events

Events participated until M18 included key exhibitions targeting the industrial community, such as Future Wine Forum or the congress Douro & Porto - Memoria+Futuro, and the presentation of project results into academic fora (e.g., the European Food Forum). In addition, project partners participated in events organised by key EU platforms / associations with a high presence of policy makers such as the EuroGEO workshop or the EIP-AGRI workshop "Farm data for better farm performance", with a significant presence of policymakers.

The list of events in which VitiGEOSS participated is collected in Table 12. Details on each action can be found on the project website <https://vitigeoss.eu/events/list/>

Table 10: List of dissemination events participated

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	PLACE	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION
------	-------	----------	-------	---------	-------------

6-15 Nov 2020	Fira de novembre	General public	Online	EUT	VitiGEOSS materials included in EUT virtual booth.
26 Nov 2020	Future Wine Forum	Wine producers, scientific community	Online	BSC	Talk in the Future of Wine Conference during the session: <i>Lessons from Spain: How wine industry can tackle sustainability and climate change.</i>
9 Dec 2020	European Food Forum	Policy makers, scientific community	Online	EUT	Project presentation during the session "Innovation in practice along the food supply chain".
16 April 2021	Workshop "European Platforms & Co-design best practices"	Policy makers, scientific community	Online	EUT, BSC, ELEAF	Participation at the discussion table organised within the workshop and presentation of VitiGEOSS as a key research and innovation project in the agri-food sector.
19-30 April 2021	European Geoscience Union (EGU) General Assembly	Scientific community	Online	BSC	Presentation "Deep learning-based downscaling of seasonal forecasts over the Iberian Peninsula" including VitiGEOSS research advances.
1 June 2021	Webinar: Artificial intelligence applied to the agri-food industry	Scientific community, industrial stakeholders	Online	EUT	Project technical presentation during a webinar with ICT start-ups, SMEs and large companies.
16 June 2021	Webinar: Sustainable solution to drought in the Aconcagua Valley	Industrial stakeholders, policy makers	Online	ELEAF	Project presentation during the session "Innovative Technologies for Irrigation and Soil Management". The presentation focused on presenting VitiGEOSS as a key project promoting a more sustainable agriculture in wine sector.
19-22 July 2021	Congresso Douro & Porto - Memoria+Futuro	Wine producers and farmers	Online	SYM	Project presentation "Emerging Technologies for Innovation in Monitoring Vineyard and Harvest Optimization in Hillside Viticulture in Douro: Case Studies at Symington" during the session "Vine - Future/ Emerging technologies".
21 Sep 2021	EuroGEO Workshop 2021	Scientific community and agri-service providers	Online	EUT, BSC, LINKS	VitiGEOSS project has been presented during the session "Advances made in EuroGEO to deliver user-oriented solutions".

12-14 Nov 2021	Fira de Novembre	Industry, general public	Online	EUT	VitiGEOSS materials (flyer, brochure) included in EUT virtual booth.
9 Dec 2021	EIP-AGRI workshop "Farm data for better farm performance"	Scientific community, industrial community	Online	EUT	Video displayed during the session "Permanent crops". A flyer was created about VitiGEOSS and was uploaded to EIP-AGRI event website. In addition, on behalf of VitiGEOSS, project technical coordinator moderated the workshop "How to involve small-medium farmers in data economies?", aiming at discussing and identifying the current barriers farmers are facing and proposing solutions for them.

VitiGEOSS platform
A single entry-point solution for wine producers, aiming to boost vineyard sustainability

Informative services

- 1 Weather and climate
- 2 Phenological monitoring
- 3 Crop status
- 4 Disease management
- 5 Business and sustainability

The project uses free-of-charge satellite imagery and EO products from the European Copernicus Programme and NASA, coupling them with in-field and near in-field data to extract useful indicators for a better management of vineyards.

The VitiGEOSS solution provides support to growers helping them to promote sustainable agriculture and a circular economy approach. VitiGEOSS' API available to be integrated together with third-party solutions and products.

Figure 20: Ernesto Bastidas, project partner from ELEAF, presenting the project during a webinar organised by the Netherlands Water Partnership

Figure 19: Project presentation during the EIP-AGRI workshop "Farm data for better farm performance"

3.6.2 Events planned

Co-design approach for probabilistic forecast

TERCILES PROBABILITIES

Figure 21: Presenting the project at EuroGEO Workshop

Project partners will continue to target national and international conferences, congresses and workshops participated by the academic community to transfer the knowledge acquired during the project. Project partners will also connect with the wine sector in national and international congresses, exhibitions and fairs to disseminate the benefits and potential of VitiGEOSS information services and platform and promote the use of project

services and EO within the industry.

A non-exhaustive list of events already identified as relevant to disseminate VitiGEOSS activities and outcomes during the second period of the project. The initial list, presented in table 13, will be periodically updated by partners.

Table 11: Identified list of academic conferences and congresses

EVENT NAME	TYPE	DATES NEXT EDITION	PARTNER	PLACE
Weather and Society	Conference	28 Feb - 11 March 2022	BSC	Online
Alimentaria	Exhibition	4-7 April, 2022	EUT	Barcelona, Spain
VINITALY	Exhibition	10-13 April, 2022	TBD	Verona, Italy
Innovate4Climate (workshop)	Conference	24-26 May, 2022	BSC	Online
4th Annual Agritech & Climate Smart Agriculture Conference	Conference	31 March, 2022	TBD	Online
Fruitlogistica	Exhibition	5-7 April, 2022	TBD	Berlin, Germany
FIMA - International Fair of Agriculture Machinery	Exhibition	26-30 April, 2022	TBD	Zaragoza, Spain
GeoSpatial World Forum	Conference	9-12 May, 2022	TBD	Amsterdam, The Netherlands
FENAVIN	Exhibition	10-12 May, 2022	TBD	Ciudad Real, Spain
PROWEIN	Exhibition	15-17 May, 2022	TBD	Dusseldorf, Germany
Living Planet Symposium 2022	Conference	23-27 May, 2022	TBD	Bonn, Germany
EU Green Week	Conference / Workshop	30 May - 5 June, 2022	EUT	Online / Brussels
VINOBLE	Exhibition	29-31 May, 2022	TBD	Alcázar de Jerez, Spain
EARSeL Workshop on Imaging Spectroscopy	Conference	22-24 June, 2022	TBD	Potsdam
Terra Clim	Congress	2-8 July, 2022	SYM	Bordeaux, France
International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium	Conference	17-22 July, 2022	TBD	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia
European Meteorological Society annual meeting	Conference	5 September, 2022	TBD	Copenhagen, Denmark
EARSeL Symposium: EU remote sensing-new solutions	Conference	13-16 September 2022	TBD	Paphos, Cyprus

European Conference on Precision Agriculture	Conference	29 Aug- 1 Sept, 2022	TBD	Vienna, Austria
FOOD TECH TRADE	Exhibition	1-3 November, 2022	TBD	Herning, Denmark
Salon International de l'Agriculture	Exhibition	February 2023	TBD	Paris, France
23 GiESCO	Congress	1 July, 2023	SYM	TBD
Adaptation Futures	Conference	2-6 October, 2023	TBD	Canada
EXPORIVE	Exhibition	8-10 November, 2023	TBD	Pordenone, Italy
SITEVI	Exhibition	28-30 November, 2023	TBD	Monpellier, France
ONEOVITI Events	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Events of the INNOVI Cluster	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Events of the Technological Platform of wine	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Events of the Foundation of Agrofood cooperatives of Catalonia	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
COPACOGECA events	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Annual Workshop of EuroGEOSS	Workshop	TBD	Online	Online
EIP-AGRI workshops	Workshops	TBD	Online / Belgium	Online
European Food Forum Events	Conference	TBD	TBD	TBD
Workshop on Complex Data Challenges in Earth Observation (CDCEO)	Workshop	TBD	TBD	TBD

ViTiGEOSS project partners will organise a series of events to disseminate project results to the industry and academic stakeholders. During project execution, partners plan the organisation of *technical webinars*, *local stakeholder events* with the wine industry and a *series of workshops* to share lessons learned, present the platform to the wine community, and disseminate the main project achievements.

3.6.3 Technical webinars

The project will organise **four technical webinars addressed to service providers** with the idea of fostering the possibility of exploitation of some particular components of the VitiGEOSS platform within the wine producer community and beyond. The organisation of webinars will be led by BSC, with the support of EUT during the event promotion. Presentations will be delivered by technical project partners.

Some details about the webinars are provided in Table 14. Webinars will be announced through the project communication channels (website and social media), and through the VitiGEOSS mailing list. The sessions will be recorded, and recordings will be uploaded to the project's YouTube channel.

Details on the general topic of the webinars and tentative dates are listed below, although they can be adjusted according to the evolution of the project advancements:

Table 12: Webinars tentative dates and topics

Proposed topic	Partner	Approximate date
Introductory webinar on VitiGEOSS project and main objectives	BSC, EUT	16 March 2022
Data analysis in agriculture	EUT	Second trimester of 2022
Probabilistic climate predictions	BSC	First trimester of 2023
Use of satellite data in agriculture	ELEAF	Second trimester of 2023

After each webinar, evaluation questionnaires will be distributed among participants to assess the satisfaction and requirements for additional webinar topics of interest.

The webinars are scheduled after the launch of the VitiGEOSS platform (M12) and on dates that do not coincide with busy periods for partners and relevant users, such as the harvest season, to ensure maximum participation and visibility of VitiGEOSS services.

3.6.3.1 Introductory webinar

The **first webinar**, scheduled on the 16th of **March 2022**, aims to introduce the project, showcase the VitiGEOSS platform for the first time, as well as bring attention to how intelligent services can help tackle the challenges faced by the wine sector. The introductory webinar can be used to create expectation and encourage the target audiences to attend the next technical webinars, while feedback gathered during the webinar will shape the subsequent webinar topics and content.

First VitiGEOSS Webinar

Intelligent services for the wine sector: Tackling current and future challenges

16th of March 2022, 10.00 – 11.00 CET, Online

The VitiGEOSS project invites you to take part in our first webinar to explore the current and future challenges of the wine sector and the use of open Earth Observation services.

During the webinar, project partners will present how VitiGEOSS is working to address the challenges by developing an **innovative vineyard management solution that integrates information on climate predictions, crop phenology, irrigation, fertilisation, disease, and business and sustainability management**. Furthermore, a sneak peek into the **VitiGEOSS platform** will be showcased for the first time, while wine producers involved in the project will give us their insights on how these services can help them to improve their operations.

At the end of the webinar, the audience will be invited to provide their thoughts and interests in an interactive session, which will help to shape the topics for the upcoming project's webinars.

Target audience:

- Viticulturists and wine producers
- Technology providers
- Viticulture and agriculture stakeholders
- Earth Observation and climate services providers
- Scientific community (in particular climate services, climate predictions, EO, satellite data)
- Other European projects

[REGISTER HERE](#)

This is the first webinar of a **series of webinars that will be organised by VitiGEOSS project to explore the use of open Earth Observation services for the improvement of viticulture operations**. In this series we will discuss the potential of services, such as those developed in the project, in **helping to optimise sustainable vineyard management while mitigating and adapting to the effects of climate change, reducing environmental impacts and promoting economic growth at the local level**.

The **European VitiGEOSS project** integrates and improves existing solutions coupling satellite imagery with in-field sensors to **increase resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to all aspects of viticulture and specific wine-business operations**. In the framework of the project innovative solutions are being developed to support agronomic management aimed at vine cultivation that integrate and improve existing solutions in the field of weather and climate forecasting, phenology, disease prediction and resource optimization.

Figure 22: View of event page on VitiGEOSS website <https://vitegeoss.eu/webinar-intelligent-services-for-the-wine-sector-tackling-current-and-future-challenges/>

During the webinar, project partners will present how VitiGEOSS is working to address the challenges by developing an innovative vineyard management solution that integrates information on climate predictions, crop phenology, irrigation, fertilisation, disease, and

business and sustainability management. Furthermore, a sneak peek into the VitiGE OSS platform will be showcased for the first time, while wine producers involved in the project will give us their insights on how these services can help them to improve their operations.

At the end of the webinar, the audience will be invited to provide their thoughts and interests in an interactive session, which will involve a live questionnaire (e.g., Menti) and an opportunity for discussion with the researchers/project partners.

Agenda	
<p>10.00 – Welcome & Introduction Marta Terrado, researcher and communicator in Earth Science, BSC Andria Nicodemou, Science communication specialist, BSC</p>	<p>10.25 – Insights from wine producers: How can intelligent services benefit viticulture? Montse Torres, Viticulture R&D Manager, Familia Torres Antonio Dente, Argonomic Manager, Mastroberardino Fernando Alves, R&D Viticulture Senior Manager, Symington</p>
<p>10.05 – Tackling current and future sustainability challenges of the wine sector Rosa Araujo, project manager and VitiGE OSS project coordinator, Eurecat Marta Otero, researcher at the Big Data & Data Science Unit, Eurecat</p>	<p>10.45 – Interactive session: Thoughts on the need for intelligent services for agriculture</p>
<p>10.20 – Sneak peek into the VitiGE OSS platform Ernesto Bastidas, Project and Business Manager, eLEAF</p>	<p>11.00 – Closing remarks & Webinar closure</p>

Figure 23: View of event agenda

3.6.4 Local stakeholder sessions

A total of three local stakeholder sessions will be organised in line with the project general assemblies.

Sessions will be addressed to **local farmers and rural communities** with the aim to educate on sustainable agricultural practices to improve productivity. These sessions will bring together **professionals from the vineyard sector and the data collection sector** to present them the capabilities and opportunities of the new sensing methods and train them about how to properly apply these technologies in their own fields.

Beyond the outreach purpose of the event, the joint participation of professionals from both disciplines will give them the opportunity to share experiences, aims and requests in order to adapt the offer from providers to the expectations of the vineyard sector practitioners.

Table 13: Preliminary dates of local stakeholder sessions

Stakeholder session	Responsible partner	Date
1 st GA	EUT / TORRES	CELEBRATED - November 19, 2021
2 nd GA	MTSA (to be confirmed)	M27-28 (November-December 2022)
3 rd GA	SYM (to be confirmed)	M39-40 (November-December 2023)

3.6.4.1 1st stakeholder session

The first local stakeholder session, organised by EUT, was celebrated on November 19, 2021. Initially planned to take place in Vilafranca del Penedès, close to Torres facilities, the consortium decided to have the event online due to Covid-19 restrictions that could hamper a successful celebration of the event. Finally, the event was organised via Teams.

The event was organised in Spanish, considering that local stakeholders such as wine growers and farmers are not fluent in English. **The workshop attracted the attention of 90 stakeholders across Spain and Latin America**, including 24 tech providers, 18 researchers, 3 members or sectorial wine associations and 45 wine producers.

1a sesión con usuarios

Servicios de viticultura de precisión para una gestión más sostenible del viñedo

19 de noviembre del 2021, 9:30 – 13.30 CET, Online

Durante este evento, presentaremos las **actividades y servicios en desarrollo del proyecto VitiGEOSS**, poniendo énfasis en **cómo se pueden aprovechar datos y recursos públicos como son los datos satelitales y su potencial para el sector de la viticultura**. También compartiremos **experiencias con viticultores** y agentes del sector del vino implicados en actividades de innovación para la digitalización del sector.

Finalmente, los asistentes podrán participar en un **workshop con entidades de la cadena valor** del sector para identificar necesidades tecnológicas, barreras y retos para la adopción de nuevos servicios como la plataforma VitiGEOSS. Estaremos encantados de contar con su participación e idear juntos posibles formas de abordar las necesidades tecnológicas del sector.

Dirigido a:

- Responsables / gestores de innovación y desarrollo de explotaciones vitivinícolas
- Directivos, responsables técnicos y profesionales de empresas vitivinícolas
- Profesionales de empresas proveedoras de tecnologías para el sector del vino
- Ingenieros e investigadores de universidades y centros de investigación

La Unión Europea es el mayor productor de vino a nivel mundial y su elaboración es la principal actividad económica de muchas zonas del sur de Europa. Es necesario **responder a los futuros desafíos de la industria del vino a partir de la innovación y desarrollo de nuevas tecnologías**, intensificando la producción de una manera sostenible y, a la vez, mitigar los efectos del cambio climático, reducir los impactos ambientales negativos y promover el crecimiento económico a nivel local.

El **proyecto europeo VITIGE OSS** utiliza los **datos abiertos de satélites de observación terrestre, maquinaria y datos de sensores instalados en el campo para mejorar la gestión de explotaciones vitivinícolas** y la sostenibilidad del sector. En el marco del proyecto, se están desarrollando soluciones innovadoras de apoyo a la gestión agronómica dirigidos al cultivo de la vid que integran y mejoran las soluciones existentes en el ámbito de la previsión meteorológica y climática, fenología, predicción de enfermedades y optimización de recursos.

Figure 24: View of 1st stakeholder event page

During this event, partners EUT, BSC, ELEAF and UNINA provided an overview of the project and the intelligent services under development in the VitiGEOSS project, emphasizing how data and public resources such as satellite data can be used and their potential for the viticulture sector. After presenting the project solutions, a round table with five local wine makers in the Penedès and Catalonia region was organised. At the round table, moderated by INNOVI Cluster Manager, the Catalan Wine Cluster, participants shared their experiences on the usage of viticulture 4.0. tools and posed challenges to VitiGEOSS partners and viticulture services providers to address specific needs.

Finally, attendees were able to participate in a workshop with entities from the wine sector value chain to identify technological needs, barriers and challenges for the adoption of new intelligent services, such as the VitiGEOSS platform.

<p>9.30 – Bienvenida e introducción a la jornada Gabriel Anzaldí, <i>Director Científico, Eurecat</i></p> <p>Mireia Torres, <i>Directora de Innovación y Conocimiento, Familia Torres</i></p> <p>9.40 – El proyecto VitiGEOSS Rosa Araujo, <i>gestora de proyectos y coordinadora proyecto VitiGEOSS, Eurecat</i></p> <p>9.55 – Herramientas innovadoras para la gestión del viñedo Modera: Xavier Domingo, <i>Director de la Unidad de Inteligencia Artificial Aplicada, Eurecat</i></p> <p>Objetivos de la plataforma VitiGEOSS Josep Pijuan, <i>Investigador de la Unidad de Inteligencia Artificial Aplicada, Eurecat</i></p> <p>Uso de pronósticos meteorológicos y climáticos avanzados Dra. Andrea Manrique, <i>Investigadora en el Departamento de Ciencias de la Tierra, Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)</i></p> <p>Predicción y monitorización de los estadios fenológicos de la vid Dr. Boris Basile, <i>Profesor Asociado en Viticultura en el Departamento de Ciencias Agrícolas, Universidad de Nápoles Federico II (UNINA)</i></p> <p>Optimización en el manejo de los viñedos por medio de información derivada de imágenes de satélite Ernesto Bastidas, <i>Gerente de Proyectos y Negocios, eLEAF</i></p> <p>Gestión de enfermedades de las vides y servicios de planificación de operaciones Josep Pijuan, <i>Investigador de la Unidad de Inteligencia Artificial Aplicada, Eurecat</i></p>	<p>11.00 – PAUSA</p> <p>11.20 – MESA REDONDA: Viticultura 4.0 y datos satelitales, la experiencia de los usuarios finales Moderador: Eloi Montcada, <i>Cluster Manager, INNOVI</i></p> <p>Participantes confirmados:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Montse Torres, <i>Responsable de R+D Viticultura, Familia Torres</i> • Agnès Nadal, <i>Responsable de Viticultura, Celler Josep Piñol</i> • Lluís Coll, <i>Responsable de Viticultura, Vallformosa</i> • Ciriac Carbó, <i>Director Técnico y enólogo, Cellers Domenys</i> • Carles Andreu, <i>Co-propietario y director de viticultura, Celler Carles Andreu, vocal en el Consell Regulador del Cava.</i> <p>12.10 – Workshop – networking: Viticultura de precisión Taller participativo con agentes del sector del vino sobre la relevancia de los servicios del proyecto VitiGEOSS y un intercambio de opiniones sobre las necesidades actuales y las soluciones más utilizadas. La sesión se llevará a cabo con herramientas innovadoras para permitir la mayor interacción posible entre todos los participantes.</p> <p>Moderan: Ana Luísa Silva, Marta Alves, Ana Rita Serras, <i>consultoras, PwC</i></p> <p>13.00 – Conclusiones workshop</p> <p>13.10 – Preguntas y respuestas</p> <p>13.20 – Cierre de la jornada</p>
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Figure 25: Event agenda

The event was recorded and the videos, as well as the presentations shown by the speakers, were sent to the attendees. The recordings are available in the event page in the following link: <https://vitigeoss.eu/local-stakeholder-event-spanish/>

Figure 26: Event recordings

Herramientas innovadoras para la gestión del viñedo

El proyecto VitiGEOSS

Mesa redonda: Viticultura 4.0 y datos satelitales

3.6.5

Participatory workshops

Two participatory workshops will be delivered from Nov 2022 to share the lessons learned, present the platform to the wine community and disseminate the main project achievements, with focus on spreading the use of Earth Observation services. The workshop organization will be led by eLEAF.

The workshops will include topics such as geo/remote sensing in agriculture (eLEAF), application of remote sensing and EO in viticulture (UNINA) and probabilistic climate forecast for decision making (BSC).

The idea was to organize the workshops as side events of renowned events or fairs, but due to the current COVID pandemic, events have been rescheduled or organized in a virtual format. Therefore, this format will also be considered for the presentation of technological developments to commercial partners, relevant stakeholders of the wine and agriculture sector or partners of other related H2020 projects. The planned workshops are listed below.

Table 14: Planned workshops

Workshop	Responsible Partners	Approximate timing
Remote sensing data for the wine industry of Europe and South Africa (virtual)	Lead: eLEAF Contributors: BSC, UNINA and other partners	November 2022
Innovate4Climate (workshop)	Lead: BSC Contributors: EUT, eLEAF and other partners	May 2022
TBD	All partners will propose upcoming events in 2023.	TBD

3.7 Scientific publications

Reports or outcomes resulting from the project activities will be published in scientific journals related to the project’s fields (partners will inform the WP6 leader and Exploitation Manager of the information to be presented publicly to avoid infringement of intellectual property rights).

Partners will ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications published via **gold open access**, whenever available (provided via the publisher when an article is published), and/or **green open access** via an online repository (Open Aire/ Zenodo) to ensure a long-term preservation and availability of the publication.

A VitiGEOSS **Zenodo community will be created** to allocate all VitiGEOSS-related research publications. Publications will be also published in researchers’ Research Gate pages (whenever applicable).

An initial list of **open access journals of interest for publishing VitiGEOSS** results has been defined, as follows:

Table 15: List of open access journals to target

Journal name
Wine & Viticulture Journal - https://winetitles.com.au/wvj/
MPDI Remote Sensing Journal - https://www.mdpi.com/journal/remotesensing
IEEE Advanced Technology for Humanity - https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8977429

International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/international-journal-of-applied-earth-observation-and-geoinformation
Remote Sensing of Environment - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/remote-sensing-of-environment
Agricultural Systems - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/agricultural-systems
Journal of Environmental Management - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-environmental-management
ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/isprs-journal-of-photogrammetry-and-remote-sensing
Computers and Electronics in Agriculture - https://www.journals.elsevier.com/computers-and-electronics-in-agriculture
Journal of Applied Remote Sensing - https://www.spiedigitallibrary.org/journals/journal-of-applied-remote-sensing?SSO=1
Journal of Remote Sensing & GIS - https://www.longdom.org/geophysics-remote-sensing.html

Research partners BSC, EUT, LINKS and UNINA will be the main responsible partners for producing scientific publications on pilots results and advancements made in the state of the art regarding weather and climate forecasting, viticulture sustainability or phenology, among other VitiGEOSS-related research topics.

Table 16: List of intended publications

Publications	Partners involved	Journal / Conference	Submitted (Y/N)
Vineyard phenology monitoring with Sentinel 3 data	LINKS	TBD	N
Vineyard phenology forecasting with in-field weather station and mid-range weather prediction	LINKS BSC	TBD	N
Diseases management	EUT	TBD	N
Subseasonal predictions, a recipe for operational implementation	BSC	Climate Services	N
Lessons learned from the co-development of an innovative vineyard management solution	BSC	TBD	N
Application of convolutional neural networks for seasonal climate forecasts downscaling	BSC	TBD	N

3.8 Training activities

VitiGEOSS partners will also disseminate project results in existing training programmes and activities, being participated or organised by their organisation (summer schools, open days, tutorials, undergraduate degrees, post-graduate, master’s courses, etc.).

Until M17, the project was presented during a lecture regarding innovative technologies for the agricultural industry.

Table 17: List of training activities M1-M17

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	PLACE	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION
Nov 2020	Robotics in Agriculture lecture	20 students	Online	EUT	Master lecture about agricultural technical solutions. Some slides about VitiGEOSS were included.

3.9 Dissemination to the society

Participation to events or initiatives for the general public to generate awareness on the project will be considered. The following initiatives have been identified:

- **International Wine Days** - Take advantage of the international wine days. Identified list of days of interest for VitiGEOSS project include the International Wine Day (each 25th May), the International Shirah day (each 22nd July), the Global Drink Wine Day (each February 18th).

Pint of Science - <https://pintofscience.com> (*each May*) The Pint of Science festival aims to deliver interesting and relevant talks on the latest science research in an accessible format to the public - mainly across bars, pubs, cafes and other public spaces. We want to provide a platform which allows people to discuss research with the people who carry it out and no prior knowledge of the subject is required.

Local Science Festivals: Barcelona Ciència - <https://www.barcelona.cat/barcelonaciencia/en/15th-science-festival> - Event for the scientific dissemination and communication to generate critical capacity, knowledge and scientific vocation. Given the current global situation, we cannot fail to address some of the issues as envisaged in the 2022 international years and plan activities to raise awareness and focus attention on the benefits of sustainable development. BSC in planning to send a proposal on one of the festival topics related on how climate change will affect the wine we drink.

3.10 Clustering activities and joint dissemination actions

During the VitiGEOSS project execution, project partners will be in contact with the coordinators of other related projects, relevant industry associations and companies, and European institutions related to the project's fields.

Synergies between VitiGEOSS and other groups has been established through attending relevant events or working groups that are organised or attended by the institutions listed in the sections below. Additionally, partners have actively interacted with the initiatives promoted by these groups and contributed with content on the project to feed associations' newsletters and publications, when possible.

3.10.1 Sister projects

Connections with other projects, initiatives and knowledge hubs with complementary interests have been sought at national, EU and international level with the aim of enhancing synergies while avoiding duplication of efforts in the dissemination of results.

Partnering with other projects and initiatives allowed to join efforts and also have a stronger voice when communicating with target audiences. Some of the VitiGEOSS sister projects and initiatives identified to date, related to the agriculture and wine sectors, climate services and/or Earth Observations, are listed in Table 17.

Table 18: VitiGEOSS sister projects

Initiative	Short description	URL
MED-GOLD	Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional Mediterranean grape, olive and durum wheat food systems	https://www.med-gold.eu/
VISCA	Climate services and Decision Support System that integrate climate, agricultural models and farmers' management specifications to adapt to climate change	https://www.visca.eu/
MEDCLIV	Experimenting with participatory approaches to design and share co-constructed adaptation (and to some extent mitigation) pathways for the vine and wine value chain in Mediterranean territories	https://medcliv.ibe.cnr.it/
AgROBOfood	New European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) to stimulate the implementation of high robotic technologies and Artificial Intelligence in the agri-food industry.	https://agrobofood.eu
IoECrops	The IoECrops project improves the productivity, efficiency and resilience of large-scale crop production by supporting agricultural management through the use of technologies based on the Internet of Things (IoT).	https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/ioe-crops/
E-Shape	e-shape is one of the nine EU-funded Environmental Observations projects that contribute to upscale Europe's Environmental Observations capacities.	https://e-shape.eu
NextGEOSS	NextGEOSS is a centralised European Earth observation data hub and platform. The concept revolves around providing the data and ICT resources needed, together with cloud services, seamlessly connected to provide an integrated ecosystem to support the deployment of Earth observation-based applications and services.	https://nextgeoss.eu/
Climate-Smart Agriculture Booster	The Climate-smart Agriculture Booster or CSA Booster is Europe's leading innovation hub, community and collaboration platform pioneering the transition to climate-smart agriculture across Europe, and around the world.	http://csabooster.climat-e-kic.org
ENVISION	Monitoring of environmental practices for sustainable agriculture supported by earth observation	https://envision-h2020.eu
NextLand	Next Generation land management services for agriculture and forestry	https://ec-nextland.eu
FIRE	An industry-led forum for innovation and research in EU earth observation	
SAFERS	Structured approaches for forest fire emergencies in resilient societies	https://safers-project.eu
SUSTUNTECH	Sustainable tuna fisheries through advanced earth observation technologies	https://www.sustuntech.eu
Coppereplace	Development and validation of a series of integrated, innovative, and viable solutions to	http://coppereplace.com

	reduce the use of copper and its environmental impact in vineyards.	
Innoseta Network	Innovative self-sustainable Thematic Network on Spraying Equipment, Training and Advising to contribute in closing the gap between the available novel high-end crop protection solutions with the everyday European agricultural practices.	http://www.innoseta.eu/aim/
AURORAL	AURORAL project aims to increase connectivity and deliver a digital environment of smart objects interoperable services platforms able to trigger dynamic rural ecosystems of innovation chains, applications and services.	https://www.auroral.eu/#/

3.10.1.1 Activities with related projects

From M1-M17, VitiGEOSS has interacted with EuroGEOSS by joining two actions groups (climate and agriculture), as well as with NextGEOSS by contributing to their data catalogue. The VitiGEOSS project has also actively participated in e-Shape project workshops and related activities.

Table 19: Activities participated with sister projects

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	PLACE	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION
19-21 Oct 2020	e-Shape General Assembly	Scientific community	Online	EUT	Project presentation, including the main project's objectives and the three different pilots, as well as the solution that will be developed and its expected results.
16 April 2021	Workshop on European Platforms & co-design best practices, e-shape and projects from topic H2020-SC5-16	Scientific community, policy makers	Online	EUT, BSC, ELEAF	VitiGEOSS participated to the workshop discussion. The event included also the participation of representatives from e-shape, FIRE, Envision, NextLand, SAFERS and SuSTunTech projects.
13 May 2021	Meeting with ENVISION	Project partners	Online	EUT	Meeting between the two projects to explore synergies and future collaboration. A conference, a common paper, a joint meeting, and social media support were mentioned by the VITIGE OSS Coordinator as possibilities of collaboration.
12 Set 2021	EuroGEO Workshop	Scientific community,	Online	EUT; BSC, ELEAF	VitiGEOSS presentation. The event also included

		policy makers, industrial community			presentations from e-shape and Africultures projects as other projects using EO for land applications.
15 Oct 2021	AURORAL project board meeting	Scientific community	Online	EUT	Presentation of the project to the AURORAL project's Catalan working group meeting. After the meeting, both projects continued to collaborate together sharing their research advances and developments and establishing networking synergies.
12 Sep 2021	EIP-AGRI workshop "Farm data for better farm performance"	Scientific community and agri-tech providers	Online	EUT	VitiGEOSS video was displayed during a project's presentation session, including also IoT Platform Nadia, Demeter, VITA, SIEGA Spot and "Digitalising vegetable irrigation" projects.

3.10.2 EU initiatives and key platforms

Cooperation and synergies will be established with relevant initiatives and platforms, some of which are listed below:

- **International Organisation of Vine and Wine (OIV)** - <https://www.oiv.int/en> - The OIV is an intergovernmental organisation of a scientific and technical nature of recognised competence for its work concerning vines, wine, wine-based beverages, table grapes, raisins and other vine-based products.
- **EU Green Deal** - https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en - The European Green Deal is the latest European plan for responding to climate change challenges by seeking carbon neutrality, and improving the well-being of people by protecting our natural habitat, among other goals.
- **COPA-COGECA** - <https://copa-cogeca.eu> - Copa (the Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations) represents over 22 million European farmers and their family members in a combined effort with its members to promote the best interests of the agricultural sector among the EU institutions and other relevant stakeholders. Cogeca (the General Confederation of Agricultural Cooperatives) represents the general and specific interests of European agri-food, forestry, and fishery cooperatives among EU institutions and other socio-economic organisations contributing to European decision making.
- **Comité Européen des entreprises vins** - www.ceev.eu - CEEV is the representative professional body of the EU industry and trade in wine gathering 23 national

associations and more than 7.000 companies, mainly SMEs, producing and selling the large majority of EU quality wines, with and without geographical indications.

- **EuroGEO** - EuroGEO is Europe’s part of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), a worldwide network working to build a Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS). EuroGEO enables Europe to position itself as a global force in Earth observation thanks to the vast knowledge gained through running the Copernicus programme and others.
- **The European Technology Platform “Food for Life”** - The Food for Life Technological Platform is the promotion of the transmission of research, scientific and technological advances through public-private collaboration of the main agri-food sector agents in relation to R&D+I and the detection of new demands in the field of Society Challenges, ensuring the competitiveness and growth of the Spanish agri-food sector.

3.10.2.1 Activities with key initiatives and platforms

From M1-M17, VitiGEOSS has interacted with EuroGEOSS by joining two actions groups (climate and agriculture), as well as with NextGEOSS by contributing to their data catalogue. The VitiGEOSS project has also actively participated in e-Shape project workshops and related activities.

Table 20: Summary of activities participated with EU initiatives and platforms

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	PLACE	PARTNER
12 Set 2021	EuroGEO Workshop	Scientific community, policy makers, industrial community	Online	EUT, BSC, ELEAF
12 Sep 2021	EIP-AGRI workshop “Farm data for better farm performance”	Scientific community and agri-tech providers	Online	EUT

4. Activities calendar

ACTIVITIES	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29
	Feb-22	Mar-22	Apr-22	May-22	Jun-22	Jul-22	Aug-22	Sep-22	Oct-22	Nov-22	Dec-22	Jan-23
D6.10 Communication and dissemination plan - Final report	X											
Technical webinar 1: Introductory webinar on VitiGEOSS project and main objectives		X										
Promotional materials update (infosheet, trifold, general presentation)			X									
Poster production			X									
2nd press release: release intelligent services			X									
Technical webinar 2: Data analysis in agriculture				X								
Poster translation into pilot sites languages				X								
Animated video				X								
Demo video production				X	X	X						
D6.6 Demo Video							X					
Local stakeholder session (Spain)										X	X	
D6.2 Middle Summary report of user engagement activities										X		
Technical webinar 3: Probabilistic Climate Predictions												X

Participatory workshop												X
	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41
	Feb-23	Mar-23	Apr-23	May-23	Jun-23	Jul-23	Aug-23	Sep-23	Oct-23	Nov-23	Dec-23	Jan-24
3 rd press release: Start of services validation in pilot sites	X											
Technical webinar 4: Use of satellite data in agriculture		X	X									
Promotional materials update (infosheet, trifold, general presentation)			X								X	
Production of infosheets on information services (update by M40)			X	X							X	
D6.7 Lessons learned in VITIGEOSS for Climate Services and Earth Observations Communities							X					
D6.12 Summary report on dissemination and communication activities and materials (1st version)							X					
2 nd demo video production								X	X	X		
Local stakeholder session (Portugal)										X	X	
Participatory workshop 2: Agritech & Climate Smart Agriculture										X		
D6.11 Demo video second version											X	
Final video										X	X	X

4 th press release: platform release												X	
													M42
5 th press release: final project results													X
D6.4 Summary report on dissemination and communication activities and materials													X
D6.5 Final summary report on user engagement activities													X
D6.8 Executive Summary													X

